

The Knowledge of Myth in Literature

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The study aims at the influence of myths in the lives of author and their works. The use of myth by the writers has led to a new type of criticism, namely myth criticism. Myth criticism analyses the works of literature based on the myths used by the authors. This sole approach of critical analysis has given rise to a need of thoughtful the concept Myth in relation to man's Considering the fact that the understanding of mythological elements that appear in art ultimately requires their re-embedding into a literary dimension where they become understandable and decipherable, literature emerges as the supreme instrument for the transportation of mythical stories. Thus, literature is not only constituted by, but also constitutive for the communication of myth.

The Knowledge of Myth in Literature

The connection between literature and myth is one of reciprocated dependence. Even though literature cannot be reduced to myth and myth cannot be reduced to literature, neither of the two can exist on its own: myth has always been an integral element of literature. Not only does it offer a warehouse of comprehensive stories for the fictional world-making of literature, which expands, modifies, or rewrites mythological elements in the process of creative reception. It also provides the narrative strategies which literature evolves from as it is indicated in Aristotle's Poetics where mythos refers to plot, to a unified construct of required and probable actions. Furthermore, as suggested by the etymology of mythos, myth epitomizes the very origin of literature, which is rooted in oral tradition and the performance of literary texts.

Rather than referring to mythos in the Aristotelian intelligence of the term, which has been treated by Northrop Frye, for instance, who conceives myth as "a structural organizing principle of literary form" (Frye 5), myth, in this paper, will be used to denote an invented, traditional story, which embodies and provides an clarification, or validation for impressive such as the early history of a society.

The analysis therefore will concentrate on the beginning of mythological narratives in classical archeological find and focus on

stories as they have been transmitted and received by Greek and Latin literature and which have henceforth served as a foundation for modern myth-making, providing the mythological documents for characters and themes in literature and art. Even though the segregation of literature and myth is not unproblematic insofar as myth cannot continue living outside literature while literature does not crumple in myth, the conflation of the two dismisses their different connection to knowledge, which, at the same time as often overlooked, is nonetheless very significant for a closer analysis of the “knowledge of literature”, which greatly relies upon,

The idea that literature might be its own form of knowledge reaches back into relic where the knowledge of literature was not always seen as being attractive or particularly advantageous as it is famously expressed by Plato’s expulsion of poets from the city in his Republic. The classification of information into the categories of knowledge and belief, however, poses an epistemological problem since it is ultimately bound to the individual’s sense of certainty rather than deriving from any kind of objective knowledge. Even as knowledge can be defined as founded and thus justifiable understanding or reproducible modes of thinking and acting, it is never static but always in process.

The knowledge of myth in William Drummond’s *The Statue of Medusa* Considering that Drummond’s epigram entitled *The Statue of Medusa* was published as early as 1616, it is remarkable that the Medusa as metaphor of literary creation, as figuration of the knowledge of myth and poetic example of the employment of mytho poetic space has not yet been fully explored. It almost seems as if psychoanalytic readings and feminist approaches of this figure, which has become a popular reference in both of these research areas have blurred a mytho- and meta poetic approach to what emerges as the key figure of the relation between the concepts of transformation and enthrallment as well as an image that is central to the dissemination of mythological knowledge in literature. Even its metamorphic quality, which constitutes the Medusa as a “travelling” image, an image which entered and continues to reside in multiple knowledge systems,²⁰ as well as its significant role in promoting the multimedia “knowledge” of literature, has been widely neglected by literary research even though literature has made extensive use of the “knowledge” of this myth:

The Statue of Medusa
Of that Medusa strange,
Who those that did her see in Rocks did change,
None Image carv’d is this;
Medusas selfe it is:
For whilst at Heat of Day,
To quench her Thirst Shee by this Spring did stay,
Her curling Snakes beholding in this Glasse,
Life did Her leave, and thus transform’d Shee was. 21

In *The Power of Myth*, Campbell talks about one of the most famous myths, the one he first explored in *The Hero with a Thousand Faces*, that of the paradigm or model of the hero. This prototype is based on bits and pieces from many different myths and legends from all over the world. The hero may defeat or conciliate this power and go alive in the kingdom of the dark or be slain by the opponent and descend in death.

In *The Power of Myth*, Campbell also focuses particularly on the Grail legend, the great myth from medieval Europe that F. Scott Fitzgerald and other artists in our time have referred to in describing the modern world as a wasteland. In this spiritually empty place, people live inauthentic lives. The grail that the knight searches for represents the fulfillment of the highest spiritual potentialities; it belongs to those who have truly lived their own lives, following their own volition and achieving harmonious relationships rooted in compassion for others.

In *A Passage to India*, E. M. Forster compares and contrasts three major religious or mythical traditions--Christianity, Islam, and Hinduism. He sardonically depicts the cooperative of British citizens desperately trying to hold together the fabric of Empire as they confuse Christianity with imperialism. They seem to live with old myths that have lost their meaning, ones that identify individuals only with their local group. The barriers that subsist to make unity among diversity difficult include nationality, religion, culture, caste, and gender. These barriers limit the horizons of characters and pervert their understanding of elementary ideas; love and compassion are reserved for members of an individual's own group.

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